

SOCIAL SCIENCES

COMPLEX GENDER INDICES: HISTORICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECT

Akbash K.

*PhD in Physic & Mathematics, Associate Professor,
ResearcherID: Z-5027-2019,
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3676-4574>*

Pasichnyk N.

*DSc in History, Professor,
ResearcherID: Q-8394-2019,
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0923-9486>*

Rizhniak R.

*DSc in History, Professor,
ResearcherID: Q-3371-2019,
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1977-9048>;
Department of Mathematics and Digital Technologies,
Volodymyr Vynnychenko Central Ukrainian State University*

ABSTRACT

The problem of gender inequality remains relevant worldwide, evolving alongside social and cultural changes. Overcoming gender disparities fosters social justice, drives economic growth, and enhances opportunities for individuals and society. This article examines the history and methodology of constructing three key gender indices: the Gender Development Index, the Gender Inequality Index, and the Global Gender Gap Index. Special attention is given to adapting these indices to the subnational level in Ukraine, considering regional socio-economic disparities, cultural factors, and the European integration context. The study highlights the importance of measuring gender inequality dynamics and proposes methodological approaches for regional adaptation, contributing to more effective resource allocation and policy development.

Keywords: complex gender indices; Gender Development Index; Gender Inequality Index; Global Gender Gap Index.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.

Relevance. The problem of gender inequality is urgent for all countries of the world. This problem is complicated and modified in the process of social and cultural changes. Overcoming gender disparities not only contributes to social equity, but also stimulates economic development, expands opportunities for individuals and society as a whole. Measuring the level of gender inequality and assessing its dynamics using complex gender indices have become important elements of the analytical practice of modern research. As part of the project under the European Union program ERASMUS-JMO-2021-MODULE “Subnational gender equality: balance of EU values and Ukrainian realities”¹ (SubGend), the history of the formation and methodology of constructing three complex gender indices (Gender Development Index - GDI, Gender Inequality Index - GII and Global Gender Gap Index - GGGI) was investigated and proposals for regional formats for their application were substantiated [1; 3; 4].

Assessing the dynamics of gender inequality and adapting gender indices to the subnational level for Ukraine is important for the following reasons. Firstly, due to the uneven socio-economic development of the regions, which affects women's and men's access to education, employment, medical services and other resources. Secondly, due to the manifestation in different regions of Ukraine of specific social traditions and cultural guidelines that can strengthen or weaken manifestations of gender inequality. The third important factor in the need to take into account the gender factor is the need for effective management, which will contribute to a more effective allocation of resources and the development of targeted programs, as well as reducing the level of social tension in modern Ukrainian society. Another significant factor in the importance of the issue of gender equality is Ukraine's European integration. Accordingly, promoting gender equality and assessing its dynamics at the national and regional levels will contribute to sustainable development and harmonization of social processes.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

The main gender indices were modified from the Human Development Index [14] based on the UN methodological calculations [15; 16]. Various options for adapting the methodology of gender indices for countries with different development characteristics have

¹ ERASMUS-JMO-2021-MODULE “Subnational gender equality: balance of EU values and Ukrainian realities”. URL: <https://cusu.edu.ua/ua/mizhnarodni-proekty/proiekt-subgend>

been proposed by European authors: an expanded regional gender gap index for Italy (Cascella, C., Williams, J., Pampaka, M., [8]), studying the variability of gender relations in Italy through the adaptation of the methodology of the European Gender Equity Index (Bericat, E., [7] and Di Bella, E., Leporatti, L., Gandullia, L., & Maggino, F., [9]), calculating the gender equality index for American states and regions (Di Noia, J., [10]), measuring structural gender equality at the state level in Mexico (Frias, S.M., [11]), analyzing the methodology of the regional Gender Equity Index in Norway (Kjeldstad, R., & Kristiansen, J.E., [18]), a report on the example of Spain on gender and regional inequality in human development (Martinez Peinado, J., & Cairo Cespedes, G., [20]), measuring gender equality in the United Kingdom (Walby, S., & Armstrong, J., [23]), development of a regional Human Development Index by the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine [19].

The authors of the article also thoroughly studied the outlined issues, namely: simple gender indices for demographic and social statistics were defined [5]; the GDI was adapted to the regional level [2] and the time series of changes in the adapted GII for the Kirovohrad region was determined [6]; the results of the adaptation of the methodology for determining the GII at the regional level for Ukraine in 2021 were presented [1]; a forecast of the GGI for Ukraine was made [4].

In this article, we will present a study of the history of the formation and improvement of the methodology for constructing two complex gender indices, which are modifications of the Human Development Index (Gender Development Index, Gender Inequality Index) and the Global Gender Gap Index.

Presentation of the main research material.

Since 1990, UN structures have accumulated significant experience in developing methodologies and conducting statistical gender research [14; 15; 16]. The UN expert report "Human Development Report" (1990) first published a methodology for calculating the Human Development Index - HDI [14], and in 1995 a methodology for calculating two human development indices taking into account the gender factor was published - the Gender Development Index and the Women's Empowerment Index [15]. In 2010, the Gender Inequality Index was introduced to replace the Women's Empowerment Index [16].

Let us briefly outline a retrospective of methodological approaches to their calculation. Complex gender indices were built on the basis of an integral indicator - the Human Development Index, which has been calculated since 1990 [14] and measures the following parameters: standard of living, literacy rate and longevity. At the national level, the Human Development Index is the overall average value of the above three parameters and is the main characteristic of the human potential of the studied territory.

Several attempts were made in 1994 to disaggregate the Human Development Index, adjusting for income inequality (for countries with available Gini coefficient data) and adapting it to the regional level by ethnic group and gender. In the Human Development Reports up to 1995, attempts were made to construct a

gender-adjusted Human Development Index. First, each of the three components of the Human Development Index was expressed as a ratio of female to male percentages. The overall HDI was then multiplied by this simple average ratio of women to men to get the gender-adjusted HDI. There were two problems with these adjustments. First, they did not link the difference between women and men to the overall level of achievement in society. Second, each society can choose a specific value for its "antipathy to gender inequality" (ϵ), depending on where it starts and what goals it wants to achieve over a period of time. In the Human Development Reports before 1995, ϵ was implicitly assumed to be zero, meaning that no policy preferences for gender equality were assumed. But politicians must make clear choices about the weight they want to give to their gender equality preferences. In the extreme case, if $\epsilon = \infty$ (infinity), only then do women's achievements receive positive weight and men's relative achievements are ignored. The illustrative calculations of the Gender Development Index and the Gender Empowerment Index in the 1995 report were based on $\epsilon = 2$ (harmonic mean), which expressed a moderate degree of inequality aversion, in order to show that even with modest weights, the gender equality profile appears insufficient for most countries. The Gender Development Index estimates the overall achievements of women and men across the three dimensions of the Human Development Index - life expectancy, educational attainment, and adjusted real income after accounting for gender inequality. However, it can be noted that the Gender Development Index is the Human Development Index adjusted for gender inequality.

In 1995, the problem of gender inequality was recognized as socially significant at the international level and for the first time, international institutions considered the issue of measuring gender inequality using complex indices using available data [15].

To develop gender indices, comprehensive indicators were proposed to identify gender gaps and calculate the negative impact of these gaps on social progress. The basic indicator of human development - the Human Development Index - is complemented in this Report by the Gender Development Index, which is calculated using the same three variables as the HDI, but taking into account inequality between women and men and the average achievements of all people combined. The report also presented a methodology for measuring the Gender Empowerment Index, which focused on women's participation in the economic, political, and professional spheres. It aimed to determine the extent to which women had gained power or voting rights and were able to participate in various aspects of public life compared to men. Unfortunately, due to data limitations, it was not possible to capture many aspects of empowerment (including at the household level, in community life, or in rural areas) in its calculation. This complex gender index focused on only three variables: income level, share of women in professional and managerial positions, and share of parliamentary seats. The calculation and analysis of the Gender Development Index and the Gender Empowerment Index were adopted as a permanent component of the Human Development

Report in 1995. This gender component was a constant reminder to policymakers that they should pay serious attention to the issue of gender equality.

Although the indicators on which the new complex gender indices were built did not capture other important dimensions of gender inequality (such as participation in public life and decision-making, household resource consumption, dignity and personal security), they became powerful determinants of women's relative status and quality of life. Paying attention to gender inequality has become a general moral, political imperative and an argument in favor of eliminating inequality in assessing overall achievements in various spheres of life.

The World Economic Forum (2006) presents a methodology for calculating the Global Gender Gap Index [21]. This index is not a modification of the Human Development Index and has its own characteristics: the index focuses on measuring gaps, not levels; captures gaps in output variables, not gaps in input variables; and classifies countries by gender equality, not by women's empowerment. The index methodology remains unchanged and covers four areas (sub-indices) on which the index is calculated (Economic Participation and Opportunity, Educational Attainment, Health and Survival, and Political Empowerment). The indicators of the Economic Participation and Opportunity sub-index are: Labour-force participation rate; Wage equality for similar work; Estimated earned income; Legislators, senior officials and managers; and Professional and technical workers. The sub-index Educational Attainment is represented by the following indicators: Literacy rate; Enrolment in primary education; Enrolment in secondary education; Enrolment in tertiary education. The subindex Health and Survival is characterized by indicators such as Sex ratio at birth and Healthy life expectancy. The sub-index Political Empowerment reflects indicators Women in parliament, Women in ministerial positions and Years with female/male head of state (last 50). The calculation of the Global Gender Gap Index is carried out in four steps: converting male and female indicators into gender parity indices; data truncation at parity benchmark; calculation of subindex scores and calculation of final scores [13].

In the 2010 Human Development Report, the Gender Empowerment Index was replaced by the Gender Inequality Index, which, together with the Gender Development Index, remains relevant today. The Gender Inequality Index was presented as another complex index, unique in that it included educational attainment, economic and political participation, and women's health issues, and also took into account frequent inequalities at the national level. This was therefore a significant advance over the then-existing global indicators of gender equality. Measuring the disadvantages faced by women raised awareness of the issues, made it possible to monitor progress towards gender equality goals, and held governments accountable. Thanks to the joint efforts of governments, civil society and international institutions such as the International Labour Organization, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the World Bank and the World

Economic Forum, the amount of published data that includes a gender perspective has increased significantly since 1990.

Thus, existing gender problems can seriously hinder the organization of rational use of human resources and, accordingly, create obstacles to the full development of society. This necessitates the calculation of complex gender indices that take into account various aspects of human life, but they do not illustrate absolute results in gender issues and require adaptation to the regional level.

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